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Dehumanization of Migrants and the Rising Far-Right in Europe: A Text Mining Analysis of Youtube

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Abstract

This study identifies the volume and form of sentiment, toxicity, and dehumanization in digital discussions targeting refugees, asylum seekers, and migrants (RASIM). 32077 comments were collected from five YouTube videos. The text mining algorithms developed on R Studio revealed that 42.1% of the comments were written in a negative tone, 19.1% contained clearly toxic content, and 17.68% included dehumanizing terms. Additionally, one dehumanizing word exists in approximately every 142 words in the comments written to videos about RASIM. Moreover, in comments containing dehumanizing keywords, a confrontational “us versus them” discourse was constructed through terms such as “invasion” or “invader”; Islamophobic terms; metaphors like “flood” were used to dehumanize and massify RASIM; and aggressive language including words like “parasite” was employed to portray them as socially dysfunctional. In this regard, it is possible to state that digital discussions reflect a concrete manifestation of the political discourse repeatedly expressed by the European far-right through mainstream channels.

Keywords: Dehumanization, Far-right, Migration, Refugees, Social Media, Text Mining.

1. INTRODUCTION

Dehumanization occurs across various life domains. Whether explicit or subtle, it affects the quality of communication between social groups and the perceptions of individuals. Dehumanization reduces the likelihood that disadvantaged groups will receive social or bureaucratic support. Dehumanization involves portraying a group using attributes that are not human characteristics. The group, which is exposed to dehumanization, is defined with demonizing terms, objects, animals, and subhuman epithets (Bar-Tal & Hammack, 2012; Haslam & Stratemeyer, 2016; Kymlicka, 2018; Panaitiu, 2020). Within the process of dehumanization, the victim’s unique individuality and the community to which they belong, including the interpersonal relationships embedded within it, are denied (Haslam & Loughnan, 2014).

By reducing targets to subhuman entities unworthy of moral consideration, dehumanization disables empathy and moral self-sanctions, paving the way for unrestricted violence and abuse (Haslam, 2006; Pizzirani & Karantzas, 2019). Subjects who have punitive authority tend to behave ruthlessly to those who are dehumanized compared to ones who were attributed with human qualities; it is also underlined that dehumanization and lessened personal responsibility increase aggressiveness (Bandura et al., 1975). The degree of social connection is another important aspect in the occurrence of dehumanization. Socially connected people are more likely to dehumanize distant others, and increasing in-group social connection can decrease the interest in different relations (Slavinskaya, 2014; Waytz & Epley, 2012). Uniquely human attributes and human nature attributes of victim groups are denied in the process of dehumanization. The denial of uniquely human attributes, such as civility, refinement, and moral sensibility, results in animalistic dehumanization; and the denial of human nature features, such as emotional responsiveness, interpersonal warmth, and cognitive openness, results in mechanistic dehumanization (Haslam, 2006; Haslam & Loughnan, 2014; Haslam et al., 2007). According to Haslam and Loughnan (2014), the denial of human uniqueness, which results in animalistic dehumanization, can cause a variety of outcomes, from blatant acts of abuse to subtle forms of dehumanization. On the other hand, mechanistic dehumanization occurs when human nature is denied; at this point, individuals are related to inanimate objects. It is possible to encounter mechanistic dehumanization in technology, medicine or other contexts where humans are objectified (p. 403). Based on the categorization proposed by Haslam (2006), animalistic dehumanization can be observed along with feelings of disgust and contempt. According to Giner-Sorolla and Russell (2019), in the context of inter-group relations, dehumanization can be related to feelings of fear and anger.

Dehumanization can result in radical actions, such as genocide, where the right of out-groups to exist is ignored (Savage, 2013), or it can lead to a discourse that shockingly and blatantly disregards (e.g. likening apes or vermin) the human qualities of an ethnic group (Haslam et al., 2007, p. 409). In this sense, degrees of humanness can be ignored in different forms, and this can be realized in a subtle or blatant manner. In blatant cases, human qualities are overtly and consciously denied by directly equating target groups with nonhuman entities. In its subtle form, dehumanization manifests as a patronizing, dismissive, and apathetic indifference toward those perceived as less than human, not as overt hatred or anger (Haslam & Loughnan, 2014; Haslam et al., 2007).

Dehumanization occurs in intergroup relations in different forms based on power balance, target-victim profile and discourse. Individuals in the United States who hold different political worldviews dehumanize each other roughly at the same rate, blatantly or subtly, by using words such as “piece of garbage,” likening the opposite group to animals and attributing them with less evolving or lack of human traits (Cassese, 2021; Martherus et al., 2021). Groups in conflict dehumanize each other and use animal metaphor in this process (Bruneau & Kteily, 2017).

Dehumanization was observed between the different racial groups. African-Americans are being exposed to blatant dehumanization with racial epithets likening them to “monkeys” or “apes” (Hairston, 2008; Panaitiu, 2020). Members of lower socio-economic status white groups have also been subjected to dehumanization, often blatantly, through labels such as “white trash” used by individuals identifying with higher socio-economic strata (Knowles, 2016). At this point, it is important to emphasize the findings of Loughnan et al. (2014) “stereotypes of low-SES people picture them as primitive, bestial and incompletely human.”

Refugees, asylum seekers, immigrants, and migrants constitute one of the most systematically dehumanized disadvantaged groups in contemporary discourse. Several studies (see Coppin, 2020; Fekonja, 2025; Wang, 2024) have abbreviated refugees, asylum seekers, immigrants, and migrants as RASIM and defined them under a single umbrella term. Within this framework, this study focuses

on the sentiment, toxicity, and themes of dehumanizing digital content targeting RASIM under the shadow of the rising far right in Europe. In this sense, it is essential to discuss dehumanization in relation to RASIM, media coverage, and the rising far right in Europe. This analysis allows us to explore the dehumanizing dimension of digital discussions that have recently evolved.

1.1. Dehumanization Against RASIM and the Role of the Media

It has been discussed that realistic threats (such as economic and security threats) and prejudice play an important role in the emergence of this perspective toward immigration and RASIM (Nassar, 2020). Previous studies have shown that RASIM has been perceived as a potential source of problems to destination countries in the context of economic, security, culture, law, and morality (Alcaraz-Mármol & Soto-Almela, 2022; Bleiker et al., 2013; Doğanay & Keneş, 2016; Esses et al., 2008; Gemi et al., 2013; Greussing & Boomgaarden, 2017; Lawlor & Tolley, 2017; McKay et al., 2012; McKay et al., 2011). The aforementioned themes can trigger anxiety about the distribution of scarce values and resources in a destination country. This may lead to conflicts between social groups, as welfare or safety concerns can foster the dehumanization of out-groups (see Nassar, 2020). It is possible to argue that perceived threat from out-groups strengthens in-group cohesion while reducing engagement with out-groups (see Waytz & Epley, 2012), which may create a ground for dehumanization.

In line with this, RASIM has been evaluated through a dichotomy of “we” vs. “them” and subsequently dehumanized. Various studies have underlined that such dichotomic discourse, which frames out-groups as threats to the status quo, has been directed at disadvantaged groups and refugees (see Alcaraz-Mármol & Soto-Almela, 2022). The pattern of “we” and “them” in discourse is associated with social dominance orientation and dehumanization. Individuals with higher levels of social dominance orientation are particularly likely to dehumanize refugees. By dehumanizing RASIM to suppress resource competition, individuals with high social dominance orientation convince themselves of their own immunity to such hardships, making it easier to ignore the subhuman conditions endured by RASIM (Esses et al., 2008). At this point, in-group members overlook their moral obligation to help others by dehumanizing out-group members.

The media portrayal of RASIM and the information conveyed to the public are crucial factors in the (non-)occurrence of dehumanization. This is because individuals rely on media coverage of asylum-seeking issues to acquire knowledge (McKay et al., 2012). Media interest in RASIM tends to increase during periods of crisis (Alcaraz-Mármol & Soto-Almela, 2022; Lawlor & Tolley, 2017). Gemi et al. (2013) stated that the media adopts a “something negative has a higher news value” perspective when reporting on RASIM. RASIM have been portrayed using words and images that strip them of human qualities. This leads to a reconstruction or distortion of reality concerning RASIM.

Lawlor and Tolley (2017, p. 969) underline that refugee-related news circulated by the press often “contains elements of conflict (e.g., security concerns)” and tends to be “proximate (e.g., a ship of migrants arriving on the city’s shore), large in scope (e.g., an influx of 25,000 refugees) and timely (e.g., recent policy changes)” due to the economics of news production. Based on a study focusing on the use of cover photos in refugee-related news published by Australian newspapers, Bleiker et al. (2013) found that RASIM were often portrayed using low-empathy images, such as photos of large groups or RASIM shown next to barbed wire fences. These visuals can associate the notion of migration with low-empathy themes such as illegality and invasion. Doğanay and Keneş (2016) remarked that fluid metaphors (e.g. wave, influx), invasion metaphors, and danger metaphors (e.g., health and security) have been employed in Turkish newspaper coverage of Syrian refugees. According to the findings of Alcaraz-Mármol and Soto-Almela (2022), refugees have been depicted in ways that strip them of their human and individual qualities, portrayed as inanimate beings, anonymous masses (through

fluid metaphors), unwanted natural disasters, or an invading army. In addition, it was indicated that 15 dehumanizing words exist in every 100 words in the news about refugees. According to Lawlor and Tolley (2017, p. 972), legitimacy is another issue the media focuses on, besides security concerns. This reinforces fears about illegality and the potential abuse of Canada's social programs. Esses et al. (2008, p. 22) underline that "information provided about the immorality of a target group may also promote the dehumanization of the group." It has also been observed that RASIM are dehumanized in the blogosphere by being defined as disgusting and dangerous organisms or parasites (Musolff, 2015). It is evident that RASIM have been negatively influenced by discourse circulated across different platforms, which reinforces the boundary between "we" and "them." Pervasive discourse diminishes compassion and potentially legitimizes punitive, hostile responses against them by portraying RASIM as a faceless mass or attributing them immoral behaviors, reinforcing an "us versus them" divide (Bleiker et al., 2013; Kirkwood, 2017). The dehumanization of RASIM can lead to prejudice and feelings of empathy or admiration being reduced. This may, in turn, affect public support for policies aimed at helping RASIM (Esses et al., 2008).

1.2. Rising Far-Right and Anti-RASIM Sentiment in Europe

According to the UNHCR (2025), 123.2 million people are currently engaged in internal or international migration, with 42.7 million holding refugee status and 8.3 million seeking asylum. Military conflicts in the Middle East and Ukraine, as well as the economic burdens experienced in the post-pandemic era, have triggered significant human mobility.

The polycrisis in Europe have strengthened populist rhetoric and contributed to the rise of the far-right. Moreover, while the far-right takes advantage of deteriorating economic conditions, it points to others as driving the national spirit into decline (Kerr & Kerr, 2025). Thus, migration is linked to the erosion of scarce resources and values. Across Europe, far-right parties opposing RASIM have been gaining strength, all of which share the common objective of halting or making migration processes more difficult. The Brothers of Italy came to power in Italy in 2022, while the Finns Party became a coalition partner in Finland. In the Netherlands, the Party for Freedom entered the cabinet following the 2024 elections, and in Slovakia, the Slovak National Party became a coalition partner in 2023 (Ambrosini, 2025; Demčišák, 2025; Söderlund & Grönlund, 2024; Verbeek & Zaslove, 2024). The elections in Germany and France, two key member states of the European Union, also reflect this trend. In 2025, Alternative für Deutschland (AfD) doubled its vote share, whereas Rassemblement National and its allies surged in France in 2024 (Le Monde, 2024; Zeier & Grün, 2025).

In Europe, far-right movements construct a fluid discourse in which RASIM is demonized in context-specific ways to legitimize their political agendas. In Greece, for example, the far-right frame migrants and Muslims as external threats to Greek culture and sovereignty. Proposals to relocate migrants to uninhabited islands accompany this dehumanizing rhetoric (Samaras, 2025, pp. 294–296). In this sense, far-right discourse builds its rhetoric on national and cultural values to promote controversial proposals and strategically attract public attention. Missier (2022), who refers to the views of various scholars and focuses on the discourse of far-right politicians in the Netherlands, highlights that far-right rhetoric in the country includes dehumanizing components that target migrants: the portrayal of refugees by some politicians as "malicious and aggressive components (p. 5)," the framing of Muslim migrants in particular as a threat to Dutch identity and democracy (p. 8); and the targeting of established politics and elites through calls to "spend money on the Dutch rather than financing the world" via anti-RASIM narratives (p. 6).

Middleton (2016) states that populist far-right parties in Europe adopt an approach that positions migrants within a security framework and rejects their social inclusion; to strengthen their claims, they

rely on xenophobic, nationalist and popular sovereignty ideologies (pp. 14-15). This situation, similar to the example in the Netherlands, facilitates the targeting of so-called established politics and elites and enables the criticism of all other policies through the lens of migration, under the claim that the true voice of the people is being expressed. In this regard, Middleton (2016), referring to the case of France, emphasizes that a populist party like the Front National (renamed National Rally after 2018) approaches the issue of migration through the lens of the exceptionalism of French culture and identity. From this ethno-cultural superiority perspective, an anti-immigrant discourse is constructed, which also points to ideas such as national isolation and policies that prioritize France's interests (p. 15). In France, far-right parties' framing of migration as a security issue has become an influencing factor to the rhetoric and policies of mainstream political actors (Eriş & Öner, 2021). In France, far-right securitized discourse against RASIM has been adopted by so-called "vigilante" groups on social media. Even, street presence of these groups was designed to maximize social media visibility and migrants are often portrayed, through hate speech, as communities that must be policed (Gardenier, 2024, p. 679).

In Germany, RASIM is a central target of far-right populist policies and politicians. AfD frames migration as an "externally driven" security threat and approaches the issue through a "crisis and security" perspective in its social media posts, aiming to establish discursive hegemony in migration debates through frequent messaging (see Slowik, 2025). Neisser (2025) highlighted that AfD's anti-immigrant rhetoric has become increasingly radicalized with each election and that the party plays a decisive role in shaping the framing agenda and patterns of migration-related debates. AfD portrays migration as a multidimensional problem and positions it as a challenge to state governance, sovereignty, internal security, legal order, the economy, cultural identity, and the welfare system (p. 26).

Youth support for far-right politics in various countries is a factor that should not be overlooked. Researchers on the 2024 European Parliament elections emphasize that far-right support is particularly strong among younger generations, especially young men, and may continue to grow (Milosav et al., 2026). Mierîna and Koroļeva (2015) explain the support for far-right ideologies among youth through both individual and contextual factors: Individual-level support for the far-right ideology is linked to nationalism and identity, socio-economic status and resource stress, political trust and knowledge, social factors, and interpersonal contact; contextual factors include local economic conditions, migration and political models, geography, and historical context.

Although far-right anti-immigrant rhetoric is shaped by local dynamics, it also has a transnational character that enables similar discourses to spread across Europe while reinforcing a "us versus them" dichotomy. Froio and Ganesh (2019) observe that digital posts on anti-immigration and economic issues are among the few topics that contribute to the transnationalization of the far-right. However, Islamophobia serves as a "transnational glue," uniting heterogeneous organizations across different political systems (p. 531). Given the transnationalization of the far-right and growing youth interest, it is crucial to examine the techno-social ecosystem where these trends intersect. New media platforms serve as key spaces for disseminating anti-RASIM discourse. Citing various scholars, Ganesh (2025) argues that the far-right exploits digital technologies and the attention economy through ideological entrepreneurship that generates biased political ideas, images, and slogans. He adds that when political influencers' micro-celebrity practices are framed as protests against mainstream media, actors use platform interactions that exceed their intended affordances (p. 6). In this context, the far-right in Europe largely builds its discourse through new media and their technical and cultural affordances. While traditional actors struggle to adapt, far-right actors quickly adjust and initiate viral discourse that shapes the broader agenda. According to Slowik (2025, p. 37) "AfD shows significantly higher engagement rates on TikTok than any other party, which increases their visibility and influence, especially among younger audiences." Leveraging the refugee crisis as a unifying theme, the German far-right uses YouTube as

an alternative platform to spread ideology, mobilize followers, and recruit members (Rauchfleisch & Kaiser, 2020). Furthermore, attention is drawn to the presence of far-right social media influencers who covertly embed extremist ideologies into their videos to evade social media regulations. These videos often leverage the restrictive nature of platforms (such as character limits on X or time constraints on TikTok) to share simplified radical narratives, employ emotionalization through personal stories, incorporate extremist ideas into entertaining content formats inherent to social media and use their parasocial communication capacities to reinforce specific movements (Rothut et al., 2024).

2. OBJECTIVES

The rise of the far-right in Europe is reflected in successive electoral victories across multiple countries. Central to far-right politics is a negative rhetoric targeting RASIM, particularly from Muslim-majority countries. This discourse not only forms the backbone of national far-right agendas but also fosters transnational alliances. Social media plays a key role in enabling local mobilization, electoral success, and cross-border far-right network creation.

In this context, this descriptive study, which employs text mining, aims to make observations regarding the digital toxic reflections of anti-RASIM rhetoric in Europe and the dehumanization of RASIM. Accordingly, it poses the following two research questions:

RQ1. What is the quantitative distribution of sentiment, toxicity, and dehumanization in the comments of YouTube videos addressing migration in Europe?

RQ2. In what ways is RASIM dehumanized in the comments of YouTube videos addressing migration in Europe?

3. METHODOLOGY

In this framework, the dataset for this study was collected from YouTube, due to three main factors: its status as one of the video platforms with the highest number of users (Statista, 2025); its positioning as a platform utilized for constructing far-right rhetoric (Rothut et al., 2024); and its suitability for large-scale data collection through the API it provides (Sui et al., 2022).

Data collection was conducted via Facepager 4.6 (Jünger & Keyling, 2020) in two stages. First, on 06.09.2025, a YouTube search using the broad keyword group “Europe migration” was performed, limited to videos from the past year, 4–20 minutes in length, and ranked by view count. Videos of this length were preferred because they demonstrated more variety in terms of the messages they contained than short videos. The five most viewed videos were then selected for comment extraction (see Table 1).

Table 1: Metrics of the Sampled YouTube Videos.

Profile of the Videos	View Count
A vlog created by a YouTuber with over 400.000 followers.	1.3 million
A video news report published by a news channel, the subject of which is RASIM in Greece.	1 million
A video news report published by a news channel focusing on the intersectionality of Greece, the United Kingdom, and RASIM.	875 thousand
A video that addresses international politics and regional developments with sensational themes, questioning why Muslims flee to Europe rather than to wealthy Muslim countries.	819 thousand
A video-podcast episode focusing on Muslim refugees in Europe.	775 thousand

Videos include news content, vlog/podcast content, and user-generated content. The potential to access diverse comments written by different user profiles and users with content consumption habits

increases. In addition, the videos used for comment collection were published by independent users, influencers, and news channels, enhancing the diversity and representativeness of user discussions. In the next stage, the video IDs were entered into Facepager 4.6. The YouTube Data API was used in this process. The API provided by the platform was preferred in the data collection process to ensure maximum compliance with platform dynamics. The ethical framework outlined by Townsend and Wallace (2017) was adopted as a starting point while analyzing social media data. In this context, a public data source was preferred. At this point, a gatekeeper is not required to access the data. Usernames were not included in the research. Furthermore, video titles were not written directly. Only videos' themes were mentioned.

At the end of the data collection process, 33901 user comments were collected. The =DETECTLANGUAGE function in Google Sheets was used to identify comment languages and empty rows. Non-English comments and blanks were removed, resulting in a final dataset of 32077 English comments.

A text mining approach grounded in the concept of quantitative content analysis was employed to analyze the collected textual data. The algorithm built in R Studio comprises the following four main components:

1. The preprocessing of user comments,
2. The integration of the sentiment, tidytext, textdata, and Detoxify libraries to detect sentiment and toxicity,
3. The identification of dehumanization using a lexicon-based filtering approach,
4. The application of Latent Dirichlet Allocation (LDA) and word co-occurrence analysis to uncover thematic clusters where dehumanization occurs and to explore how migrants are dehumanized.

3.1. Preprocessing of User Comments

All comments were lowercased, and whitespace was used to replace non-alphabetic characters (e.g., numbers, punctuation, emojis). The extra spaces and leading/trailing spaces were removed. Comments were then tokenized, and lemmatization was applied to reduce words to their base forms. These preprocessing steps aimed to enhance the detection accuracy of toxicity and dehumanization.

3.2. Sentiment and Toxicity Detection in User Comments

The Detoxify model (UnitaryAI, 2021) was integrated into the algorithm at this stage. Detoxify is described as an open-source library used for detecting inappropriate or harmful text in online environments (Hanu et al., 2021). Su and Thakur (2025) note that Detoxify is built on BERT and considers the context and interdependence of words during text analysis. They define Detoxify as “fine-tuned on a dataset annotated for toxic language, which enables it to detect multiple forms of toxicity, including hate speech, insults and threats” (p. 718). Recently, Detoxify has been observed as a commonly used tool in studies focusing on toxic content within the digital ecosystem (e.g., Su & Thakur, 2025; Tretiakov et al., 2025). Detoxify evaluates the toxicity level of a given text by generating values between 0 and 1 (Yousefi et al., 2024). Within the framework of the study, the values between 0 and 1 have been divided into 8 categories in order to observe levels of toxicity in the comments in detail. These numerical categories have been assigned names on a spectrum ranging from Extremely Low Toxicity to Extremely High Toxicity in order to make the data visualization process comprehensible (see Table 2). Because this category serves as a midpoint in the fourth position of the eightfold system, comments with values exceeding 0.375 are classified as toxic. Moreover, as borderline content is being pointed out as a digital information ecosystem challenge by European Commission (e.g. European Commission, 2024), maintaining the threshold below 0.5 carries the potential to offer functional utility.

Table 2: Toxicity Categorization of the Comments.

Detoxify Score	Category
0 - 0.125	Extremely Low Toxicity
0.125+ - 0.250	Very Low Toxicity
0.250+ - 0.375	Low Toxicity
0.375+ - 0.5	Significant Toxicity
0.5+ - 0.625	Highly-Significant Toxicity
0.625+ - 0.750	High Toxicity
0.750+ - 0.875	Very High Toxicity
0.875+ - 1	Extremely High Toxicity

The framework proposed by Schweinberger (2026) was adopted in the sentiment analysis process. The backbone of the analysis relied on the *syuzhet* (Jockers, 2017), *sentimentr* (Rinker, 2021), *tidytext* (Silge & Robinson, 2016), and *textdata* (Hvitfeldt & Silge, 2026) libraries. Additionally, the word-emotion association lexicon developed by Mohammad and Turney (2013) was used. As a result of this process, each comment was assigned a negative, neutral, or positive sentiment label. Additionally, the number of words associated with anger, disgust, fear, sadness, trust, anticipation, surprise, and joy was identified within the comments.

3.3. Lexicon-Based Filtering Process

A list of 126 dehumanizing and inhumanizing keywords, identified in previous studies as commonly appearing in digital content targeting RASIM, was compiled in the first stage of the lexicon-based filtering process. Considering this list, the algorithm scanned user comments for keywords matching those in the list to determine whether a comment contained dehumanizing content.

3.4. Thematic Analysis of Dehumanization via LDA Topic Modelling and Word Co-Occurrence Analysis

An unsupervised Latent Dirichlet Allocation (LDA) model was employed for topic modeling to explore the thematic structure of comments containing dehumanization. This process was conducted in R Studio and was based on the *topicmodels* package (Grün & Hornik, 2011) and *ldatuning* (Murzintcev, 2024). Initially, the comments were processed using stopword filtering and lemmatization. Subsequently, the *ldatuning* package was used to determine the optimal number of clusters based on the specific characteristics of the dataset and to identify the main discussion themes within these clusters based on word distributions.

In addition to the LDA process, a word co-occurrence analysis was performed. The dehumanizing keywords were positioned as a benchmark, and the analysis identified the other words that most frequently co-occurred with these keywords in the user comments. Furthermore, the terms used to describe RASIM (refugee, asylum seeker, immigrant, and migrant) were analyzed to determine which dehumanizing words they most frequently appeared alongside. This provided further insight into the representation and characterization of RASIM in the discourse.

4. RESULTS

To answer RQ1, the comments' toxicity levels were categorized based on their Detoxify scores. Comments with a toxicity score above 0.375 accounted for 19.1% of the total dataset. Among the comments classified as toxic, 10.7% fell under the Very High Toxicity or Extremely High Toxicity categories (see

Figure 1). Although the distribution of toxicity levels across toxic comments is generally balanced, the proportion of comments classified as Extremely High Toxicity stands out as notably higher.

Figure 1: Toxicity Level in User Comments.

While the analysis shows that comments with higher toxicity levels, starting from the Significant Toxicity category, tend to contain dehumanizing content at higher rates, the proportions of dehumanizing comments in other categories (except Extremely Low Toxicity) do not differ drastically (see Table 3). It was found that one dehumanizing word exists in approximately every 142 words in the comments written to videos about RASIM.

Table 3: Level of Dehumanization in User Comments.

Category	Comment Count	Dehumanizing Comment Count	Dehumanizing Comment Ratio
Extremely Low Toxicity	22670	2647	11.68%
Very Low Toxicity	2074	362	17.45%
Low Toxicity	1202	210	17.47%
Significant Toxicity	918	173	18.85%
Highly Significant Toxicity	862	149	17.29%
High Toxicity	901	197	21.86%
Very High Toxicity	1158	228	19.69%
Extremely High Toxicity	2292	393	17.15%

The results of the sentiment analysis indicate that 42.1% of the comments carried a negative tone, 44% were neutral, and 14% were positive in nature (see Figure 2). Furthermore, words associated with the emotion of fear were the most frequently used in the comments (N=31397), followed by those related to anger (N=23890). The least frequently used emotion-related words in the context of emotion analysis were those associated with surprise (N=11568) and joy (N=13706).

To answer RQ2, the topic modeling process revealed that comments containing dehumanizing expressions toward RASIM are distributed across 10 distinct thematic clusters (see Figure 3). The findings allow for the exploration of the subjects affected by migration, the perceived characteristics of RASIM, the ways in which migration is conceptualized and the secondary actors and attitudes associated with migration.

Figure 2: Sentiment of User Comments.

The ways in which RASIM is portrayed vary depending on the videos' thematic and regional focus. Word frequency patterns suggest that RASIM is often perceived as African, Eastern, or Arab in Western contexts. In this context, certain comments include terms such as “trash” or “garbage” when referring to RASIM, while others describe their movement as an “invasion” and label them as “invaders.” RASIM is also described using terms such as “flood,” which emphasize massiveness. In addition to this term, other words that evoke a sense of mass movement, such as “wave” or “influx,” are also occasionally used. RASIM is frequently associated with the “illegal” keyword, which carries a legally reductionist implication. Notably, there are contexts in which migration as a whole is described as illegal in a generalized and oversimplifying manner. Moreover, RASIM is frequently dehumanized by being associated with crime and labeled as “criminal,” thereby stripped of individual human characteristics. It should also be noted that there is a recurring narrative emphasizing that government-collected taxes are spent on “illegal immigrants invading the country” and that RASIM “live for free” in the countries to which they migrate.

RASIM and Islam are frequently discussed in the comments within a clearly intersecting domain. RASIM is portrayed as individuals from Muslim-majority countries, adhering to Islam, demanding Sharia law in host countries, and being uncivil, anti-Western, and anti-Christian. In some instances, migration to the West is even characterized as “religious migration.” According to Table 4, which displays word co-occurrences, the words “Islam” and “cancer” were found to co-occur most frequently within the same sentence. In Cluster 5 (see Figure 3), the frequent appearance of the word “kill” in association with “Islam” and “Muslim” is particularly worrying. In addition to defamatory comments suggesting that RASIM from Muslim-majority countries are present “to kill” in the host countries, comments that encourage hate actions against RASIM have also been observed.

At this point, it is important to examine how calls to action against RASIM are framed within comments that include dehumanizing language. Notably, word clusters that call for sending RASIM back to their countries of origin are recurring, while disregarding the factors that forced them to migrate in the first place. In this context, comments frequently include imperative keywords, such as “send them back” or “deport,” without considering the RASIM's current conditions or circumstances. In comments containing dehumanizing content, RASIM is often positioned as a destructive object and

framed within a dichotomy of “them versus us.” A recurring perspective suggests that RASIM poses a threat to European countries and their people. Particularly, their growing numbers are perceived as a danger to European culture, lifestyle, and overall demographic and social structures. Furthermore, they are framed as a risk to the economy, legal frameworks, and belief systems of host societies. In comments containing dehumanizing content, political actors are also frequently mentioned. This finding points to countries known for their anti-immigration stances where new far-right policies are on the rise. In this context, references to countries such as Poland and Greece, as well as politicians like Trump, have been observed.

Figure 3: Themes of Discussions based on the LDA Topic Modeling Process.

A word co-occurrence analysis was also conducted to identify the words that most frequently appeared in the same sentence with dehumanizing terms in user discussions (see Table 4). In this context, the three most frequently occurring dehumanizing keywords in the comments were “illegal,” “invasion,” and “invader.” Each of these dehumanizing keywords most frequently co-occurred with the word “country.” In fact, “country” emerged as one of the most frequently co-occurring terms within the same sentences as dehumanizing language. This co-occurrence suggests a discursive construction in which RASIM is positioned not as a part of the host society but as an external force, almost as an occupying power. This finding is further supported by the frequent use of mass-describing terms such as “flood” and “wave.” These terms reflect a discursive structure that strips RASIM of individuality and context, framing them as a mass, coordinated force rather than as individuals with individual stories. Moreover, in digital discussions about RASIM, dehumanizing terms such as “cancer,” “animal,” “parasite,” “snake,” “dog,” and “rat” are among the most frequently observed. Words such as “virus,” which frequently co-occur with the term “like,” are used to emphasize the growing population of

RASIM in host countries. Metaphors such as “multiplying like a virus” or “They are like a virus” frame RASIM as a dangerous phenomenon that must be eliminated.

Table 4: Most Frequently Co-Occurring Words with Dehumanizing Terms Within the Same Sentence.

Keyword	Most Co-Occurrent Word	Frequency	Keyword	Most Co-Occurrent word	Frequency
Illegal	Country	483	Overrun	Country	26
Invasion	Country	209	Parasite	Country	26
Invader	Country	111	Snake	Grass	21
Refuse	Country	76	Savage	Country	18
Flood	Country	72	Wave	Country	17
Alien	Illegal	58	Barbarian	Country	16
Kick	Country	54	Filthy	Country	16
Cancer	Islam	41	Dog	Like	15
Trash	Country	41	Rat	Country	15
Garbage	Country	34	Virus	Like	15
Animal	Country	33	Waste	Country	15

Another word co-occurrence analysis was conducted to identify which dehumanizing keywords most frequently appeared in comments containing the terms “refugee,” “asylum seeker,” “immigrant,” and “migrant” (see Table 5). The findings at this stage offer supporting evidence that enables a deeper exploration of the dehumanization of RASIM. All four descriptors of RASIM most frequently co-occurred in the same sentence with the dehumanizing keywords “illegal,” “invasion,” and “invader.” Other prominent keywords identified through the co-occurrence analysis include “influx” and “flood,” both of which portray RASIM as a mass phenomenon. Additionally, terms such as “parasite,” which target the societal position of RASIM in a dehumanizing manner, and action-oriented keywords such as “kick” and “refuse,” which imply a call for action against RASIM, have also been frequently observed.

Table 5: Word Co-Occurrence of RASIM Descriptors with Dehumanizing Terms.

Migrant	Immigrant	Refugee	Asylum Seeker
Illegal, 199 co-occurrence	Illegal, 334 co-occurrence	Illegal, 59 co-occurrence	Illegal, 43 co-occurrence
Invasion, 51 co-occurrence	Invasion, 29 co-occurrence	Invader, 58 co-occurrence	Invader, 43 co-occurrence
Invader, 30 co-occurrence	Flood, 27 co-occurrence	Invasion, 40 co-occurrence	Invasion, 15 co-occurrence
Flood, 22 co-occurrence	Invader, 20 co-occurrence	Influx, 11 co-occurrence	Parasite, 7 co-occurrence
Kick, 12 co-occurrence	Refuse, 16 co-occurrence	Flood, 10 co-occurrence	Alien, 2 co-occurrence

5. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

The rising far-right political discourse in Europe is also reflected in digital debates that depersonalize RASIM, position them as a threat and make them the target of dehumanization. It is possible to state that one out of every 142 words in the comments have dehumanizing characteristics. This indicates that dehumanization has become normalized by removing the barriers to abusive and violent acts (Haslam, 2006; Pizzirani & Karantzias, 2019) within the digital ecosystem, and it constructs a violent world that is grounded in the digital sphere under the shadow of the rising far-right. Furthermore, the lack of variation in the dehumanization rate across comments ranging from “Extremely High Toxicity” to “Extremely Low Toxicity” suggests that the dehumanization of RASIM is rendered ordinary, either directly or subtly, in every dimension of digital debates.

The findings of the study demonstrate that 42.1% of digital debates regarding RASIM contain negative

sentiment and that the most frequently encountered emotions are related to fear (N=31397) and anger (N=23890). Giner-Sorolla and Russell (2019) pointed out that dehumanization may be associated with the emotions of fear and anger within the dynamics of inter-group relations. Consequently, the findings of this study align with Giner-Sorolla and Russell's (2019) perspective. This context allows for a discussion on how RASIM may be perceived as the initiator of a corrosion of scarce resources and values. Consequently, such a perception may cause fear and anger, leading to the dehumanization of this group. The characterization of RASIM by far-right actors as a threat, malicious, and aggressive (Missier, 2022; Samaras, 2025), as highlighted in previous studies, and the confinement of the migration issue within a crisis and security framework (Slowik, 2025) are also observed in this study exploring the situation in the digital field. In digital debates, the words "illegal" and "invader" are frequently used in a dehumanizing context, and the socio-economic and humanitarian reasons triggering the migration of RASIM are pushed into the shadow of a legitimacy and security-based questioning. Considering the frequently co-occurring words, the frequent use of dehumanizing words together with the word "country" indicates the framework's widespread use on digital platforms, overlapping with the far-right narrative, which claims that RASIM is an organized threat to independence, culture, and traditions. Additionally, similar to previous studies (see Alcaraz-Mármol & Soto-Almela, 2022; Doğanay & Keneş, 2016), RASIM are also intensely depicted in digital debates with dehumanizing words such as "wave" and "influx." This situation points to a language that functionalizes the in-group vs. out-group dynamics inherent in dehumanization; it causes the public to feel under an organized and mass threat, and the state of cognitive uncertainty emerging from fear facilitates the creation of fear-based policies targeting "established politics" by the far right through RASIM. The targeting of Islam and Muslims in comments carrying dehumanizing characteristics also facilitates the functioning of the "us versus them" dynamics common in far-right political discourse. Considering the previous studies, it may create a supportive narrative ground for the development of transnational networks to accelerate the spread of the far-right (see Caiani, 2025; Froio & Ganesh, 2019; Keşkekci, 2025).

Findings show that the digital reflections of far-right political narratives circulate extensively, and a widespread negative emotion exists toward RASIM, who are victims of humanitarian crises in the age of polycrises. Furthermore, a concept that strengthens the "us versus them" mindset toward RASIM, encourages violence, and dehumanizes RASIM within the framework of crisis and security is being widely produced.

Considering the findings and previous studies, developing policy implications and platform governance recommendations to combat digital hate and dehumanization is possible. The dehumanization of RASIM on digital platforms is a collective narrative that arises from the coming together of singular comments through platform possibilities and interaction. Combating the mass nature of this discriminatory digital narrative is possible by developing a collective user stance and culture by empowering users. In the construction of this culture, it is possible to adapt the roadmap developed by Vraga et al. (2020) for combating the infodemic. Although this roadmap was developed to combat misinformation, it also provides an intellectual ground for combating other forms of online toxic content. In line with this, users must be empowered and users must possess a news literacy capacity to distinguish between good and bad information. Furthermore, users should be included in a user culture that will make it possible to report discriminatory content, produce content that can contribute to social cohesion, and promote such content. Finally, platforms should construct a user culture that makes it possible to combat discriminatory content. In addition, it is important to make content moderation algorithms more effective and participatory. Within this framework, Wilson and Land (2021) highlight the issue of opacity in AI-based content moderation processes and draw attention to the importance of reliable users/organizations in combating digital hate speech. In line with this perspective, ensuring

algorithmic transparency and including users/specialists in the construction process of automated content moderation algorithms to combat digital dehumanization holds potential advantages.

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